
Enhanced hydroxyl radical scavenging activity by doping lanthanum in ceria nanocubes

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Abstract

Ceria nanoparticles have been reported to possess special antioxidant and catalytic properties due to their unique redox characteristics. In this study, single-crystalline CeO₂ nanocubes were synthesized which demonstrated hydroxyl radical scavenging properties. In order to further enhance such activity, lanthanum (La) was doped into the nanocubes, for the first time, 10%La doped CeO₂ nanocubes were synthesized by a hydrothermal method. The as-synthesized, La modified, ceria nanocubes presented improved radical scavenging activity spanning a range of concentrations and durations. The structure and redox behavior of the nanocubes were characterized using X-ray diffraction (XRD), ICP, X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy (XPS), High Resolution Electron Microscopy (HREM), temperature programmed reduction (TPR) and oxygen storage capacity (OSC), etc. A mechanism was proposed on how the incorporation of La could affect the redox as well as scavenging properties of CeO₂ nanocubes. This new nanomaterial may be potentially used as protective agent in bioapplications.

1. INTRODUCTION

Ceria and CeO₂-containing materials have been extensively investigated in heterogeneous catalysis ^{1, 2} and solid oxide fuel cells ³. Recently, CeO₂ nanoparticles have also been found to exhibit good antioxidant activity in many medical treatments because of their unique redox properties and good biocompatibility ⁴⁻¹². The antioxidant activity of ceria has been commonly recognized due to its ability of scavenging free radicals ⁴⁻¹⁴, such as superoxide ($\cdot\text{O}_2^-$) and hydroxyl radicals ($\cdot\text{OH}$), which is related to the ability of ceria to switch between Ce⁴⁺/Ce³⁺ oxidation states. For example, the hydroxyl radical scavenging activity of ceria nanoparticles was first observed directly by Xue et al. using nanoceria of different sizes ⁵. It was found that ceria nanoparticles can protect part of methyl violet (MV) from being oxidized by hydroxyl radical as Ce³⁺ was oxidized to Ce⁴⁺. In that contribution, it was also claimed that there was a close correlation between the hydroxyl radical scavenging activity and the amount of Ce³⁺ on the surface of the nanoparticles ⁵, which directly affects the redox cycle of ceria.

During the last decade, attempts have been made in order to control and enhance the redox and antioxidant properties of nanoceria. These focused mainly on two aspects: through the control of the morphology of the ceria nanocrystals and, secondly, through doping nanoceria with other elements. So far, the successful synthesis of morphology controlled ceria nanorods, ceria nanocubes, ceria nanooctahedra and ceria nanotubes has made progress on catalytic activity for CO oxidation ¹⁵, total oxidation of polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons ¹⁶, NO reduction ¹⁷, soot combustion ¹⁸, H₂ oxidation ¹⁹, and so

on. It was found that ceria nanorods (110-facet dominant), ceria nanocubes (100-facet dominant) and ceria octahedral (111-facet dominant) exhibit different catalytic activities, for example for CO oxidation, in the order of nanorods > nanocubes > octahedra ¹⁵. In terms of hydroxyl radical scavenging activity, the influence order is nanoparticles (15-20 nm) < nanobars (6-15 nm) < nanowires (~7 nm) ⁶. It was found that the amount of Ce³⁺ on the surface of these three kinds of ceria is quite similar, implying that the amount of Ce³⁺ is not the only reason for the difference in antioxidant property as used to explain the behavior of ceria nanoparticles ⁵. It seems reasonable that the ability to regenerate Ce³⁺, namely redox activity, also contributes to the hydroxyl radical scavenging activity, as suggested from data in CO-TPR experiments ⁶.

Alternatively, doping ceria with another elements, such as transition metals (Zr) or other lanthanides (La, Pr), has been proven to improve its redox properties due to the increase of the concentration of oxygen vacancies and oxygen mobility in ceria ²⁰⁻²⁷. The ionic radius of La³⁺ (103.2 pm) is very close to that of Ce⁴⁺ (87 pm) ²⁸, and thus, La can easily incorporate into the crystal lattice of CeO₂ and promote the mobility of anionic vacancies ²⁹. Doping of CeO₂ with La can inhibit the sintering of the nanoparticles and increase the reducibility of ceria by decreasing the temperatures at which reduction of ceria starts to be significant. In parallel, improvements in the catalytic performance for soot combustion have been already reported ³⁰. The addition of La also promoted the formation of oxygen vacancies and surface superoxide ions, which lead to higher catalytic activities for methane combustion ³¹. Au catalysts supported on La-doped ceria nanorods and nanoparticles have also been

synthesized and their catalytic activities have been evaluated for water gas shift and CO oxidation reactions^{32, 33}.

In spite of several studies focusing on the antioxidant properties of ceria nanoparticles^{10, 11, 34}, there are few reports yet on the antioxidant activity of doped nanoceria, such as that related to the hydroxyl radical scavenging activity. Ghibelli et al. studied the redox-dependent mechanism of nanoceria with increasing Sm³⁺ doping. Their results evidence that Ce³⁺/Ce⁴⁺ redox reactions are responsible for the in vivo anti-aging and anti-inflammatory effects on leukocyte cell lines³⁵. Meanwhile, Pr doped mesoporous ceria solid solutions have been proven to be an efficient photocatalyst for degradation of Rhodamine B (Rh B)³⁶, which is related to the radical oxidation because the addition of Pr in 2-D mesoporous ceria improves the formation of oxygen vacancies.

In this work, the cubic morphology has been chosen because crystal facets of nanocubes are more uniform than in other morphologies of nanoceria. Both pure and lanthanum modified ceria nanocubes have been synthesized and studied for hydroxyl radical scavenging activity for the first time. Their structure and redox behavior have also been investigated in order to understand the mechanism of hydroxyl radical scavenging.

2. EXPERIMENTAL

2.1. Synthesis

A hydrothermal method previously described in the literature³⁷ was used, with some modifications, for the synthesis of the samples. Thus, to prepare the reference sample, CeO₂ nanocubes (NC), 125 mL of 11.5 M NaOH (Alfa Aesar,

98%) and 115 mL of 0.1 M $\text{Ce}(\text{NO}_3)_3 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (Alfa Aesar, 99.5%) were mixed and stirred in a Teflon container of a maximum volume of 300 mL for 30 minutes. After that, the Teflon container was sealed with a Teflon tap and introduced into a stainless steel autoclave. The reaction mixture was kept at 180 °C for 24 h into an electric oven. Then, the mixture was cooled down to room temperature, it was centrifuged, washed with deionised water several times and then once with ethanol (Panreac, Absolute Ethanol). A yellowish powder was obtained. Finally, the samples were dried at 80 °C for 24 h in an oven.

The preparation of the 10%La-CeO₂ NC sample was carried out following the same procedure as mentioned before except that the concentrations of Ce and La precursors were adjusted accordingly. In the case of the 10%La-CeO₂ NC sample, a 0.094 M in $\text{Ce}(\text{NO}_3)_3 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$ and 0.01 M in $\text{La}(\text{NO}_3)_3 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (Sigma Aldrich, 99.99%) solution was used.

2.2. Physical and compositional characterization

X-Ray Diffraction (XRD) patterns were recorded on a D8 ADVANCE diffractometer of Bruker using the Cu K α radiation, with a range of 5°-110°, a step of 0.02° and a step time of 1s. The software DiffracPlus was used to measure the width of the (111) diffraction peak of ceria nanocubes in order to calculate the particle size using the Scherrer equation.

To determine the actual La content of the doped nanocubes, Inductively Coupled Plasma (ICP) measurements were carried out using an ICP-AES Iris Intrepid equipment of Thermal Elemental.

X-Ray Photoelectron Spectroscopy (XPS) analyses were performed on a Kratos Axis Ultra DLD instrument. Spectra were recorded using monochromatized Al K α radiation (1486.6 eV), with an X-ray power of 150 W. The spectrometer was operated in the Constant Analyser Energy (CAE) mode, with pass energy of 20 eV. Powder samples were pressed into pellets, which were stuck on a double-sided adhesive conducting polymer tape. Surface charging effects were compensated by making use of the Kratos coaxial neutralization system. The binding energy (BE) scale was calibrated with respect to the C 1s signal at 284.8 eV.

The samples were also investigated using a variety of Transmission and Scanning-Transmission Electron Microscopy techniques. These analyses were all performed in a JEOL 2010-F scanning-transmission electron microscope with 0.19 nm spatial resolution at Scherzer defocus conditions in high resolution electron microscopy mode (HREM). High angle annular dark field–scanning transmission electron microscopy images (HAADF-STEM) were obtained by using an electron probe of 0.5 nm of diameter at a camera length of 8 cm. Electron Energy Loss Spectroscopy (EELS) analyses were carried out by using an ENFINA spectrometer (Gatan), using a convergence angle of 1.82 mrad, a collection angle of 0.64 mrad, an exposure times of 1 second with a dispersion of 0.3 eV/channel and an aperture of 5 mm.

Brunauer-Emmett-Teller (BET) surface areas of the samples were determined in a Micromeritics ASAP 2020 via nitrogen adsorption at -196 °C. Prior to the analysis, the samples were degasified at 150 °C for 2 hours under vacuum.

2.3. Antioxidant activity

The antioxidant activity of the samples was studied by investigating their capability to scavenge the hydroxyl radicals from Fenton reagent in a methyl violet (MV) reaction solution. The nanocubes were dispersed in 0.1 M Tris-HCl pH4.4 buffer and sonicated prior to use. The reaction solution used for the photometric determination contained 2.4×10^{-5} M MV, 0.3 mM FeSO₄ and 0.4 M H₂O₂ in 0.1 M Tris-HCl pH 4.4 buffer. To quantify the photometric change before and after sample addition, the reaction solution was blended for 1 min at room temperature before measuring the UV-vis absorption spectrum through a SHIMADZU UV-2450 spectrophotometer. The concentrations of CeO₂ NC and 10%La-CeO₂ NC were varied in order to study the influence of this parameter on hydroxyl radical scavenging activity. All the chemicals used above were purchased from Sigma-Aldrich (US).

2.4. Redox properties characterization

Temperature programmed reduction with H₂ (H₂-TPR) analyses started with a pretreatment consisting in an oxidation under a 5% O₂/He flow (60 mL/min) at 500 °C for 1 hour. After the oxidation pretreatment, the samples were cooled in the same 5% O₂/He flow down to 150 °C, and then the flow was changed to pure He down to room temperature. The samples were reduced in a 60 mL/min flow of 5% H₂/Ar with a heating rate of 10 °C/min and a maximum reduction temperature of 950 °C, keeping the sample at this final temperature for 1 hour. The H₂-TPR analyses were measured via a Thermostar GSD301T1 mass spectrometer of Pfeiffer Vacuum. The mass/charge ratio (m/z) value used to monitor H₂ consumption was 2 and 18 for the concomitant formation of H₂O.

Oxygen Storage Capacity (OSC) measurements were carried out by a thermogravimetric method, using a SDT Q600 horizontal thermobalance. The pretreatment used in these experiments was an oxidation in a 5% O₂/He flow at 500 °C for 1 hour. Then the sample was cooled down in the same flow to 150 °C, and kept at this temperature for 30 minutes. The process of analysis consisted in measuring the weight loss of the sample in a 5% H₂/Ar flow, with a flowrate of 60 mL/min, at isothermal regime at selected increasing temperatures (200 °C, 350 °C, 500 °C and 700 °C). To proceed from one temperature to the following, a heating rate of 10 °C/min was used and upon reaching the desired temperature, it was held for 1 hour. The reduction degree of cerium was calculated based on the total weight loss of the sample, which was considered to be only due to the consumption of lattice oxygen of ceria to produce water.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1. Structure and composition of ceria nanocubes

To study the structure of the synthesized samples, XRD analyses have been performed and are shown in Figure 1(a). All the diffraction peaks present in both CeO₂ NC and 10%La-CeO₂ NC samples can be indexed to fluorite-like, face-centered cubic structure (Fm3m), ceria. However, in the sample that contains La, a slight shift of 0.1° to smaller angles of the (111) peak is observed, which can be clearly seen in the enlargement of the diagrams shown in Figure 1(b). This effect can be attributed to the larger ionic radius of La³⁺ (103.2 pm), as compared to that of Ce⁴⁺ (87 pm).²⁸ This observation points out to an effective incorporation of La into the CeO₂ lattice to form a solid solution^{27, 30, 32, 33}. This was confirmed by the calculation of the lattice parameters using the (111)

XRD peak in both diagrams, Table 1. Note that the lattice parameter estimated for the 10%La-CeO₂ NC sample is 5.44 Å, which is just slightly larger than that of CeO₂ NC (5.42 Å). From the full width at half maximum of the XRD peaks and using the Scherrer equation, the size of the single crystals for CeO₂ NC and 10%La-CeO₂ NC were also calculated, these being 21 nm and 28 nm, respectively (Table 1).

The composition of both samples was determined by ICP. As shown in Table 1, the molar concentration of La is 10.3%, which is very similar to the expected value. The surface composition of the La-modified ceria nanocubes (first 4.5 nm layer from the surface)³⁸ was determined by XPS. A 10.3% La content was also found using this surface specific technique. As listed in Table 1, the composition results from XPS coincide with those obtained by ICP, which represent the composition of the whole crystals. These results clearly indicate that the in depth distribution of La in the 10%La-CeO₂ NC sample is very homogeneous.

XPS analyses also allow us to study the chemical state of La and Ce. In Figure 2 (a), the La 3d_{5/2} spectrum corresponding to the 10%La-CeO₂ NC sample is shown. This spectrum consists of a main photoemission peak centered at 833.7 eV, followed by a shake-up satellite structure, centered 5.1 eV above. As discussed in the literature³⁹⁻⁴¹, the position of the shake-up satellite and its relative intensity with respect to the main photoemission peak in La 3d_{5/2} spectrum, is indicative of the chemical environment of the La(III) ions in the sample. As can be seen in Figure SI.1, the comparison of La 3d_{5/2} in the La-doped ceria sample with other reference compounds containing lanthanum,

allows us to conclude that La ions are in a pure oxide environment. As shown in the literature ^{40, 41}, when lanthanum is not incorporated into ceria structure, it reacts with atmospheric water and CO₂, producing hydroxide or hydroxycarbonate compounds. This fact can be noted by changes in the position and relative intensity of the two above mentioned peaks in the La 3d_{5/2} signals, as can be seen in Figure SI.1 for aged lanthanum oxide. As the spectrum recorded for 10%La-CeO₂ NC corresponds to lanthanum in an oxide environment, we can conclude that all La (III) detected close to the surface is well integrated into the cerium oxide lattice as a solid solution.

The oxidation state of surface cerium can also be quantitatively measured by the detailed analysis of the Ce 3d core level, as shown in Figure 2 (b). It is well known that Ce 3d spectrum is rather complicated, showing a multiplet structure consisting of a set of 5 doublets when Ce³⁺ and Ce⁴⁺ coexist in the sample ⁴². To avoid possible errors in the fitting procedure of the spectra using such a large number of peaks, to obtain cerium reduction degree, two reference spectra were used, corresponding to samples with either 100% Ce³⁺ or 100% Ce⁴⁺. By combination of these two references, the experimental spectra were fitted, as shown in Figure 2 (b), being the obtained reduction degree 1.5% Ce³⁺ for CeO₂ NC and 2.5% for 10%La-CeO₂ NC. These results, as it will be seen later, are in good agreement with EELS data obtained for the first 4.5 nm from the surface of the nanocubes. In conclusion, incorporation of lanthanum in the ceria lattice does not significantly affect cerium oxidation state, despite the greater amount of oxygen vacancies that substitution of tetravalent cerium by trivalent lanthanum should produce.

The homogeneity in the chemical composition of 10%La-CeO₂ NC sample and the oxidation states of Ce were also investigated at a higher spatial resolution (down to 0.5 nm) by spectrum-line EELS analyses. In this type of experiments, EELS spectra of the 10%La-CeO₂ NC were acquired point by point, every 0.5 nm, along lines on the nanocubes starting at one surface, crossing through the bulk of the material and exiting at the opposite surface, as marked on the HAADF-STEM image shown in Figure 3(a). The whole collection of spectra, Figure SI.2, were then qualitatively and quantitatively analysed to determine the spatial distribution of both lanthanide elements, Ce and La. Figures 3(a1) and 3(a2) show the intensity profiles extracted from the HAADF-STEM image along the line used in the spectrum line experiment (number 2) and a perpendicular one (number 1). Note, importantly, that the first profile appears basically flat whereas the second depicts a homogeneous growth towards the center of the image. Since, for a given composition, the intensity of HAADF-STEM images changes roughly linearly with thickness, these intensity profiles indicate that the Electron Energy Loss spectra were obtained along a path of roughly constant thickness, at the thickest part of one of the cubes which was oriented perpendicularly to one of its edges, i.e. along close to one of its [110] zone axis. This constant thickness condition allows a much direct comparison of the EELS results.

As clearly observed in Figure SI.2, the M_{4,5} peaks of both elements, La and Ce, are present in all the spectra throughout the path, from the surface to the bulk, with intensities which do not vary significantly. Moreover, the intensities of the M_{4,5} signals of La are smaller than those of Ce. The composition in all the

points was also analysed in quantitative terms and very similar La contents were determined (13 ± 3 at. %).

Together with the results obtained from by ICP and XPS, we can conclude that the composition of 10%La-CeO₂ NC is very homogeneous, La being mixed with Ce at atomic level. This is in agreement with conclusions reported on the structure of nanocrystalline cuboidal La doped ceria by Basu et al⁴³. They have investigated the shape evolution of nanocrystalline lanthanum doped ceria under the influence of the electron beam irradiation and pointed out to a homogeneous distribution of the dopant on the basis of Energy-Filtered Images (EFTEM). In any case, it is important to note that, although experimental EFTEM images are not displayed in this paper, the spatial resolution routinely achievable with this technique is worse than that characteristic of the STEM-based spectrum-line approach used here.

A final question that deserves a comment regarding the EELS Spectrum-line experiments refers to the oxidation state of Ce. It is well known that the fine structure of the Ce-M_{4,5} edge is quite sensitive to changes from Ce³⁺ to Ce⁴⁺, this being reflected in changes in the exact energy position of the two white lines, their relative intensities and the appearance of extra shoulders at the high energy side in the case of Ce⁴⁺. At a qualitative level, the change in relative intensities of the two peaks is the most easily detected feature (see reference spectra gathered in Figure SI.2).

To discuss in more detail this aspect, Figure 3(b) shows EELS spectra extracted from different locations of the spectrum line collection of Figure SI.2. In particular, spectrum 3 corresponds to the average of the 4 spectra recorded

at the top-most surface positions of the cube (first 1 nm layer). In this average, two spectra come from the entrance surface and the other two from the exit surface. Spectrum 3 thus depicts the state of the elements at pure surface sites. Spectrum 2 corresponds to the average of 18 spectra recorded from the surface but considering a thicker layer, down to a 4.5 nm depth. As before, 9 spectra come from the entrance surface and the rest from the exit surface. This average spectrum would carry information comparable, from the same volume, to that in XPS. Finally, spectrum 1 averages 70 spectra corresponding to bulk positions, i.e. at distances beyond 4.5 nm from the two surfaces.

If we fix our attention in the details of the fine structure, spectra 1 and 2 correspond to a nearly fully oxidised state, with a negligible contribution of Ce^{3+} species. In contrast, spectrum 3 indicates that a significant fraction of the Ce atoms exposed at the first surface layer consist of Ce^{3+} species. Note at this respect how, in difference to that observed in spectra 1 and 2, the intensity of the M_5 line is higher than that of the M_4 . Though these results suggest that Ce is reduced just at the very first atomic planes, it is not possible to determine how much of this reduction is due to beam damage effects, i.e. to reduction under the electron beam. This means that even in this first surface layer a mixture of both Ce^{3+} and Ce^{4+} must be present. Likewise, it is also very important to indicate at this respect that in Spectrum-line experiments performed on the pure CeO_2 NC sample the average spectra corresponding to the first 1 nm layer of this sample also depicts Ce predominantly as Ce^{3+} species.

Therefore, Spectrum-Line EELS experiments are fully compatible with data obtained by XPS, which show a very close distribution of Ce oxidation

states in the first 4.5 nm layers in the two samples, the pure and La-doped one. EELS analysis, which allow a much higher spatial resolution, points out to a content in reduced Ce species at the top-most surface layers much larger than that measured by XPS ($\approx 2\%$), but still shows no difference between the two oxide samples.

3.2. Morphology of the ceria nanocubes

Figure 4 shows representative HREM and HAADF-STEM images for both CeO_2 NC and 10%La- CeO_2 NC. In both cases, these 2D images agree with cubic-shaped crystals. The analysis of the spatial frequencies observed in the HREM images (Digital Diffraction Pattern, DDP, included as insets), Figures 4(c) through 4(f), reveals the presence of the $\{002\}$ and $\{111\}$ reflections of fluorite-type ceria. The former are observed in the images recorded along the $[001]$ zone axis, Figures 4(c) and 4(d), whereas the latter are detected in those along the $[110]$ direction, Figures 4(e) and 4(f). The very slight differences between the lattice parameters of CeO_2 and the 10%La- CeO_2 samples leads to quite subtle changes in the spacing of the $\{200\}$ and $\{111\}$ planes between the two oxides, which fall out the accuracy achievable in measurements performed on HREM images ($\approx 5\%$). According to this analysis of the HREM images, the surfaces of the crystallites would consist of $\{001\}$ type of planes, i.e. the samples are constituted by $\{001\}$ -bounded nanocubes.

In contrast to previous observations reported by Basu et al.⁴³ for the La-doped cubes, the $\{001\}$ planes exposed on both samples appear rather smooth. In any case both types of cubes are affected by corner rounding effects, specially in the case of the sample made of pure CeO_2 . Such rounding, also

reported in previous works, involves a small contribution of both {110} and {111} type facets to the overall crystal shape.^{37, 44} Figure SI. 3 gathers additional images, which provide further support to these conclusions about the crystal shape.

The defects in the edges and corners just described are extremely important in catalysis; e.g. Au nanoparticles tend to deposit on areas corresponding to edges and corners of ceria nanocubes³⁷.

The synthesized CeO₂ NC and 10%La-CeO₂ NC samples are of different sizes, and their particle size distributions, established from the TEM/STEM study, are presented in Figure 5. These were built after measuring the edge length of roughly 150 nanocubes for each sample. It can be seen that the edge-length distributions of the two samples are very similar, both spanning the 5 to 50 nm range but with most of the nanocubes below 35 nm. From the distributions, the volume-averaged cube sizes could be calculated. The values obtained were 22 and 27 nm for the CeO₂ NC and 10%La-CeO₂ NC samples respectively. These results are very close to the values calculated from the Scherrer equation using XRD the (111) peak at 28.6°, as listed in Table 1. So, in average, the size of the cubes present in the 10%La-CeO₂ NC sample is very similar, just slightly larger, than that of those in CeO₂ NC.

The edge length distributions allow also obtaining an estimation of the specific surface area of the two samples, by assuming in first approach a model of non-truncated, perfect, cubes. The values so obtained, included in Table 1, were 33 m²/g for CeO₂ NC and 25 m²/g for 10%La-CeO₂ NC. In fact, these

values are very close to the specific BET surface areas obtained by N₂ physisorption measurements, 38 m²/g and 25 m²/g.

Finally, an estimation of the contribution of the different type of crystallographic planes to the total exposed surface could be done, starting from measurements of the length of the edges and roundings. Thus, the percentage of {100}, {110}, and {111} facets in the CeO₂ NC have been analyzed to be 84%, 16% and < 1%, as previously reported³⁷. For 10%La-CeO₂ NC, the corresponding percentages are 91%, 9% and 0% for the same facets.

3.3 Antioxidant activity

The antioxidant activity of ceria nanocubes was determined by their ability to scavenge the free hydroxyl radicals produced by the Fenton reaction. The Fenton reagents, Fe²⁺ and H₂O₂ in acidic aqueous solution, react to generate hydroxyl radicals which quickly oxidize purple MV into the colorless oxidized MV (OX-MV), as indicated in Eqs. (1) and (2)^{5,6}.

The decolorization of MV can be measured and quantified through its absorption at $\lambda_{\text{max}}=584$ nm, which is linearly related with the concentration of purple MV. Therefore the absorption change at 584 nm indirectly indicates the quantity of $\cdot\text{OH}$ in solution.

The black curve in Figure 6 represents the absorbance of purple MV (24 μM) at its peak wavelength, 584 nm. After the Fenton reagents (0.3 mM Fe²⁺ and 0.4 M H₂O₂) were added to MV and mixed for 1 minute, the absorbance dropped, being represented by the red curve, which suggests that part of MV

has been oxidized and hence decolorized. Fe^{2+} , H_2O_2 and 10%La-CeO₂ NC individually has almost no absorbance at 584 nm (data not shown) and they have no effect on the MV absorbance, in agreement with previous reports ⁵. Therefore, the absorbance drop and MV oxidization were most likely induced by the free radicals generated by the Fenton reaction in Eq. (1). 1 minute incubation with Fenton reaction can reduce the absorbance of MV from 0.6 to 0.5. Based on the linear relationship between absorbance and concentration, this means that more than 16% of MV has been oxidized in this time interval.

Figure 6 also shows an enhancement in the absorbance when the 10%La-CeO₂ NC sample is incorporated to the system, which suggests that it is capable to scavenge the $\cdot\text{OH}$ radicals. The absorbance of MV shifts upward gradually, towards the value of original MV, when the concentration of 10%La-CeO₂ NC added to the solution is increased from 1 to 100 nM. This indicates that either more MV is protected from the radical oxidization or that less free radicals are present in the reaction medium as the concentration of 10%La-CeO₂ NC increases. Figure 7 demonstrates the increase of absorbance with 10%La-CeO₂ NC concentration spanning a wide concentration range, from 10⁻² nM up to 100 μM , and the inset presents the corresponding trend of color change with increased 10%La-CeO₂ NC.

Generally speaking, with the presence of antioxidant nanocubes, there are three processes taking place: Fenton reaction in Eq. (1), oxidation of MV in Eq. (2) and elimination of hydroxyl radicals. Figure 8 presents the absorbance changes with 1, 10 and 100 nM nanocubes of 10%La-CeO₂ NC and CeO₂ NC. The reference curve (black) shows that the MV absorbance keeps dropping with the incubation time, which means that the radicals are continuously generated

by the Fenton reaction. This is the combined results of the first two processes. In the presence of 10% La-CeO₂ (blue) or CeO₂ (red) NCs in the mixture, the MV absorbance values decrease slightly with incubation time during first 20 min. This suggests the occurrence of an inhibition effect on MV oxidation. The inhibition effect is stronger for 10%La-CeO₂ NC than CeO₂ NC. This, however, is the consequence of all the three processes. To understand the evolution of absorbance with time, it is necessary to take account this process as mentioned in the previous. Thus, it appears that the elimination of radicals is a slower process than the other two, which is why there is a decrease with time in absorbance. Subtracting the reference curve from the curves with NCs, the absorbance change ΔA from solely the hydroxyl inhibition and its kinetics can be obtained. For example, the changes from 10 nM 10%La-CeO₂ and CeO₂ NCs over a longer incubation time are compared in Figure 9. The ΔA data is linearly related with the amount of protected MV from oxidation, representing the capability of NCs to scavenge the hydroxyl radicals. The elimination rate, denoted as slope of data in Figure 9, varies with time. The kinetics can be divided into two stages, the initial first stage (yellow region) is short and fast and the later second stage (blue region) is long and slow. The first stage is possibly due to the consumption of active sites on the nanocubes while the second stage may be associated with the cycling of Ce³⁺ and the corresponding elimination of radicals. In this first stage, it was estimated that the atoms of Ce on the surface of the doped sample are 3.4 times more active than those of the ceria nanocubes. Similar kinetic profiles have also been observed for other concentrations of NCs. This could be interesting and potentially useful to improve intrinsically the kinetics of the radical degradation process.

Ceria nanoparticles have been already successfully used in biomedical applications on mammalian cells in normal and diseased state^{10, 11, 45}. Most of their effects, such as neuroprotection, attribute to ceria nanoparticles a certain capability to scavenge free radicals, including reactive oxygen species (ROS) and hydroxyl radicals. Since the initial reports on nanoceria as radical scavenger, more attention has been focused on the improvement of methods to synthesize biocompatible and more importantly more antioxidant nanoceria related biomaterials. In this study, Figures 6 to 9 have provided clues about a significant improvement in the antioxidant activity of CeO₂ NCs doped with 10% of La. To the best of our knowledge, this is the first time that a La modified ceria with controlled morphology was reported to exhibit such enhanced antioxidant activity.

3.4. Redox property of ceria nanocubes

As previously reported for nanoceria^{5, 11, 46}, the antioxidant activity is most likely related to the redox properties of ceria, that is, the ability to continuously cycle between Ce³⁺ and Ce⁴⁺ oxidation states. Previous reports have linked the antioxidant capability with the amount of Ce³⁺ and the regeneration of Ce³⁺ at the surface of nanoceria.⁵⁻⁶ In order to examine redox properties of ceria nanocubes and investigate their relationship with their hydroxyl scavenging activity, temperature programmed reduction with H₂ (H₂-TPR) together with OSC measurements were carried out on both CeO₂ NC and 10%La-CeO₂ NC.

3.4.1 H₂-TPR characterisation

Figure 10 shows the H₂-TPR profiles of the ceria nanocubes following the H₂O evolution. The corresponding H₂ consumption signal can be seen in Supporting Information Figure SI.4. The CeO₂ NC reference sample presents a first small peak about 527 °C, followed by another rather wide high intensity signal peaking at 830 °C. These two peaks can be attributed to surface and bulk reduction of the ceria nanocubes, respectively. According to other studies, this sample shows a reduction profile similar to that of conventional ceria nanoparticles¹⁹. Here, the reduction peak attributed to reduction of the surface of the CeO₂ NC sample appears at a slightly lower temperature, this suggesting that Ce⁴⁺ can be more easily reduced to Ce³⁺ on nanocubes than on nanoparticles.

As shown in Figure 10, the introduction of lanthanum has improved the reducibility of the nanocubes at low temperatures, by shifting the reduction events at lower temperatures, as expected. Thus, in the case of 10%La-CeO₂ NC, the evolution of the H₂O signal starts around 370 °C as in the undoped reference sample but the whole profile moves down the temperature scale. It is observed in the most intense peak which now reaches its maximum at 732 °C. In other words, the incorporation of La into CeO₂ not only reduced the nanocubes at lower temperatures, but also promoted of the mobility oxygen within the structure. Bo Zhang et al.³¹ have presented a study about the obtaining of La-Ce mixed oxide nanoparticles with different molar compositions prepared by sol-gel method. They have reported that the incorporation of lanthanum into CeO₂ promotes the formation of oxygen vacancies and superoxide ions. On the other hand, W.Y. Hernández et al.²⁷ have synthesized La doped ceria nanoparticles using a coprecipitation method. The reduction

temperatures of $\text{Ce}_{0.9}\text{La}_{0.1}\text{O}_{2-\delta}$ are very similar to those in our study (446 and 523 °C low temperature peak and 723 °C high temperature peak). They proposed that the incorporation of La in the CeO_2 structure caused an increase in the formation of oxygen vacancies this leading to improvements in oxide ion mobility and, concomitantly, in reducibility.

3.4.2 OSC measurements

In order to quantify the amount of Ce^{4+} can be reduced on both types of nanocubes, Oxygen Storage Capacity (OSC) measurements were performed (Figure 11). Figure 11 (a) shows that the 10%La- CeO_2 NC presents a larger oxygen weight loss (35.8 mmol O/mol oxide) at 500 °C than the undoped CeO_2 NCs (31.3 mmol O/mol oxide). This indicates that the reducibility of 10%La- CeO_2 NC is higher than that of CeO_2 NC, which is in agreement with the H_2 -TPR results commented above. When the temperature was increased up to 700 °C, the weight loss of both samples increases but the amount of cerium which can be reduced in 10%La- CeO_2 NC is still higher than that in CeO_2 NC. Since La does not participate in the reduction reaction due to its unique La^{3+} oxidation state, the amount of atomic oxygen released by the samples corresponds only to ceria⁴⁷. The reduction degrees of Ce at different temperatures can be calculated based on the weight loss of the samples, as shown in Figure 11b. It was found that 28% of Ce^{4+} can be reduced to Ce^{3+} for 10%La- CeO_2 NC at 700 °C, while only 17% of Ce^{4+} can be reduced for CeO_2 NC. This means that at the same temperature more Ce^{4+} can be reduced to Ce^{3+} in 10%La- CeO_2 NC than in CeO_2 NC. Hence ceria reduction becomes easier in the La doped nanocubes. The incorporation of La may favour oxygen migration, through the creation of oxygen vacancies. This seems to favourably impact further elimination of

oxygen from the lattice. Francesca Deganello et al.²² have analyzed the OSC of different samples containing La and Ce. They found that the oxygen uptake ability is independent of the surface area or crystallite size, but increase with La incorporation or La:Ce molar ratio as long as the ratio is lower than 0.18. In this study the La:Ce ratio is ca. 0.11 (10/90), in line with their observation.

3.5. Quantification of the hydroxyl radical scavenging activity of ceria-based nanocubes.

Xue et al. have proven that the decrease of MV absorption changes after addition of ceria nanoparticles to a MV solution is due to the consumption of hydroxyl radicals by ceria⁵. In this study, such activity has been tested on ceria nanocubes with controlled morphology and the effect of La incorporation into nanocubes has been also investigated. First, the influence of nanocubes on protecting MV from hydroxyl radical can be estimated. The concentration of MV is 2.4×10^{-5} M, whose absorption is 0.6. The addition of Fenton reagent to MV solution leads to the decrease of MV absorption to 0.456 after 20 min of incubation. As it was observed in Figure 8 (a), the absorbance of MV decreases only to 0.498 when 10%La-CeO₂ NC is in MV solution, which can be attributed to a partial elimination of hydroxyl radicals by 10%La-CeO₂ NC. The absorbance difference between the solution containing 10%La-CeO₂ NC and without 10%La-CeO₂ NC corresponds to the amount of MV which was protected by 10%La-CeO₂ NC. At 584 nm, the MV absorbance is linear to its concentration. Then the percentage of MV protected by 10%La-CeO₂ NC is 7%. Similarly, the percentage for undoped CeO₂ NC is 6.3%. Comparatively, the percentage of MV protected by 1nM ceria nanoparticle as studied before is ca.

2%.⁵ This suggests that in terms of hydroxyl scavenging activity, the 10%La-CeO₂ NC is much more effective than CeO₂ NC and nanoparticles.

The volume of each solution is 2 mL, so the amount of MV protected by 10%La-CeO₂ NC is 3.36×10⁻⁶ mmol. The concentration of 10%La-CeO₂ NC is 1 nM and the total amount of 10%La-CeO₂ NC in the solution is 2×10⁻⁹ mmol, which is more than three orders of magnitude less than the protected MV. This means that in average one mole of 10%La-CeO₂ is capable of scavenging hydroxyl radical and protect over thousands of moles of MV molecules from oxidization.

Knowing that Ce³⁺ is crucial to the scavenging activity of ceria^{5, 11, 35} and the fraction of initial Ce³⁺ on 10%La-CeO₂ surface is only 2.5%, it seems reasonable to propose that a mechanism to regenerate Ce³⁺ in the MV solution must be operating, which allows the operation of the Ce³⁺/Ce⁴⁺ redox cycle. The strong oxidative ·OH radical may oxidize Ce³⁺ to Ce⁴⁺, then Ce⁴⁺ could be reduced to Ce³⁺ under acidic conditions as in Eq. (3) and (4)^{5, 6, 8, 11-13, 48}. The Ce³⁺ regeneration process is extremely important in the reversible redox-cycle exchanging Ce³⁺ and Ce⁴⁺. This redox cycle occurs after the consumption of initial active sites on the NCs as observed in Fig. 9 and it enables the continuous elimination of hydroxyl radicals.

Figures 6 to 9 have demonstrated that 10%La-CeO₂ NC has higher antioxidant activity than the undoped CeO₂ NC. This observation coincides with the redox characterization of both samples using H₂-TPR and OSC measurement. In the H₂-TPR profiles (Figure 10), the peak area indicates the

amount of regenerated Ce^{3+} and the peak location in temperature suggests the level of difficulty of this Ce^{3+} regeneration.⁴⁹ Comparing the TPR of CeO_2 NC with that of 10%La- CeO_2 NC, it can be seen that the peaks in 10%La- CeO_2 NC occurs at lower temperatures than in CeO_2 NC, which means that the transformation from Ce^{4+} to Ce^{3+} , is easier and faster for 10%La- CeO_2 NC. On the other hand, OSC results also show that the reducibility of 10%La- CeO_2 NC is higher than that of CeO_2 NC, with reduction degrees (fraction of Ce^{3+}) at 700 °C of 28% and 17% respectively. These results suggest that the stronger antioxidant properties of 10%La- CeO_2 NC could be attributed to its higher reducibility.⁶

As antioxidant, the 10%La- CeO_2 NC has demonstrated a significantly higher activity than CeO_2 NC. At least three different sources could contribute to this behaviour. First, although the La doped NC contains almost same fraction of Ce^{3+} (~2%) on the surface than the undoped CeO_2 NC (~2%), it is observed a favourable effect on the scavenging of hydroxyl radicals in the sample which contains lanthanum. Nevertheless, if one takes into account that the specific surface area of the La-doped sample is much smaller than that of the non-doped CeO_2 NC sample, roughly 65%, and also that 10% of the lanthanides exposed at this surface correspond to La^{3+} species in the doped material, the total number of Ce^{3+} sites available at the surface, for the same amount of moles of the two solids, could be considerably smaller in the La-doped sample. Therefore, the total number of available Ce^{3+} species cannot clearly be the factor influencing the improvement observed with the La-doped nanocubes.

Secondly, the 10%La- CeO_2 NC sample exhibits better redox properties than CeO_2 NC, which is a decisive factor for the regeneration of Ce^{3+} species

during the hydroxyl radical scavenging process. The last one, the La doped NC exposes more active surface facets than the undoped one. At this respect, it is widely accepted that for ceria the surface activity of the main low-index surfaces lies in the order (100) > (110) > (111), which is linked to their ability to assimilate oxygen vacancies and oxygen mobility in them⁵⁰⁻⁵³. Therefore the 10%La-CeO₂ NC with 91% (100) facets could exceed the activity of CeO₂ NC, which only expose 84% of (100) facets, in terms of the recycling rate of Ce³⁺, i.e. the reaction rate of Eq. (4). A faster Ce³⁺ recycling rate would enable our synthesized 10%La-CeO₂ NC to exhibit a more efficient antioxidant activity than the undoped CeO₂ NC. Considering the expanding application of nanoceria in radical scavenging and tissue protection, these La-doped ceria nanocubes may become potentially helpful and advantageous with respect to conventional ceria nanoparticles in biological treatment.

4. CONCLUSIONS

In this study, single-crystalline CeO₂ nanocubes were synthesized which demonstrated hydroxyl radical scavenging properties. Furthermore the doping of 10% La in the nanocubes enhanced such activity. The as-synthesized La modified ceria nanocubes presented an enhanced radical scavenging activity spanning a range of concentration and duration. The improved redox properties and changes in the crystallographic composition of the facets exposed at the surface seem to be responsible of the improved radical scavenging activity of La-doped ceria nanocubes. This new material may be potentially used as protective agent in bioapplications.

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Table 1 Composition and textual results of the CeO₂ NC and 10%La-CeO₂ NC samples

	BET surface areas (m ² /g)	Calculated surface area (m ² /g) ^a	Composition by ICP (mol%)		Composition by XPS (mol%)		Average particle size (nm) ^a	τ Scherrer (nm) ^b	Lattice parameter (Å) ^b
			Ce	La	Ce	La			
CeO ₂ NC	38	33	-	-	-	-	22	21	5.42
10%La-CeO ₂ NC	25	25	89.7	10.3	89.7	10.3	27	28	5.44

a) Calculated as an average of 100 nanoparticles measured by TEM

b) Calculated by Scherrer equation using XRD data

Figure 1(a) XRD diagrams of the CeO₂ NC and 10%La-CeO₂. (b) Zoom on the (111) peak of both samples. A 0.1° shift to a smaller angle is observed for the 10%La-CeO₂ sample.

Figure 2 XPS spectra corresponding to (a) La 3d_{5/2} in the 10%La-CeO₂ NC sample and (b) Ce 3d in both 10%La-CeO₂ NC and CeO₂ NC.

Figure 3 (a) HAADF-STEM image of one of the cubes in the 10%La-CeO₂ NC sample. The type of path used in the spectrum-line EELS experiments performed on this sample is marked for illustration (line 1). Two intensity profiles along the two paths (1 and 2) marked on the HAADF-STEM image are shown in the right side; (b) EELS spectra, in the La-Ce M_{4,5} energy loss region, representative of different locations of the Spectrum-line experiment recorded along the path marked as 1 in (a): (1) average of 70 spectra at the bulk of the nanocube; (2) average of the spectra corresponding to the first 4.5 nm from the surface; (3) average of 4 spectra corresponding to the first 1 nm surface layer.

Figure 4 HAADF-STEM images of (a) CeO₂ NC and (b) 10%La-CeO₂ NC; HREM images of (c), (e) CeO₂ NC and (d), (f) 10%La-CeO₂ NC samples in the [001] and [110] zone axis (DDPs shown as insets).

Figure 5 Edge length distributions of a) CeO₂ NC and b) 10%La-CeO₂ NC.

Figure 6 UV-vis absorption spectrum of MV for MV with Fenton reagent and 10%La-CeO₂ NC sample of 0 (red), 1 (blue), 10 (green) and 100 (purple) nM concentration. The black line is the reference peak for sole MV solution with specific peak at 584 nm. The curves for 1 nM (blue) and 10 nM (green) 10%La-CeO₂ NC are too close so they appear overlapped.

Figure 7 Increase of absorption at 584 nm with increasing 10%La-CeO₂ NC concentration. The inset demonstrates the color change of MV after the Fenton reaction in presence of 10%La-CeO₂ NC from low to high concentration.

Figure 8 MV absorbance (584 nm) change in MV/Fenton reagents mixture over incubation time from 1 to 20 minute under the conditions of (a) 1 nM, (b) 10 nM and (c) 100 nM nanocubes. For each condition, the effect of 10%La-CeO₂ NC was compared with CeO₂ NC together with the reference (no CeO₂).

Figure 9 The absorbance change ΔA over the incubation time for MV mixed solution with Fenton reagents and 10 nM CeO_2 or 10% La-CeO_2 NCs. The kinetics profiles are divided into an initial fast stage (in yellow) and a later slowly stage (in blue). The lines indicate the linear rate of absorbance change.

Figure 10 H₂-TPR profiles of the nanocube samples. The m/z: 18 signal corresponds to H₂O evolution.

Figure 11 (a) OSC measurements for the CeO₂ NC and 10%La-CeO₂ NC samples.
(b) Reduction degree of Ce for the same samples.